

Fourier Analysis of The Random Ray Method for k-eigenvalue Problems

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we investigate the convergence behaviour of The Random Ray Method (TRRM) using Fourier analysis. The approach taken includes the inherent stochastic noise present in TRRM. The theory developed in this study predicts the mean and variance of the spectral radius of the TRRM iterative scheme in terms of the problem and ray parameters. The analytic expression for the mean predicts a small additive correction to the standard source iteration result, with the correction tending to zero for long ray lengths. We find that TRRM is unconditionally stable across all parameter ranges investigated. Due to stochastic noise, it is possible that “transients” in the convergence emerge where error modes grow (the eigenvalue for a given error mode can sometimes be greater than 1), but on average, all error modes decay. The predictions are then compared to values measured using the neutron transport code SCONE, and the measured mean spectral radius was found to closely match predictions. The standard deviation of the spectral radius can be computed and agrees well with simulation.

Keywords: The random ray method, neutron transport, method of characteristics, Fourier analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The Random Ray Method has been developed in recent years as a new approach to solving the neutron transport equation [1, 2]. Analysis so far has shown promising results in terms of performance in comparison to both deterministic and Monte Carlo methods, particularly for 3D problems [3]. However, the inherent stability and convergence properties of this method have not yet been formally investigated.

This goal of this paper is to derive and verify theoretical predictions of the iterative stability and convergence properties of TRRM using Fourier analysis. In particular, we aim to predict how TRRM parameters, such as the ray length, impact the spectral radius, which is a measure of the asymptotic rate of convergence of the iterative scheme. This provides the basic theory which can be extended to understanding random ray’s behaviour under more complicated circumstances, e.g., with convergence acceleration [4] or multiphysics.

Fourier analysis (also referred to as “Von Neumann analysis”) has frequently been employed to examine the convergence of fixed point iteration schemes involving differential equations, including the neutron transport equation [5]. In this work, the Fourier analysis is comprised of two main steps. First, a first-order approximation is used near the converged solution to linearise the differential equations. A Fourier *ansatz* is then employed to represent the eigenvector of the set of equations, corresponding to a specific Fourier wave number. This allows the linearised equations to be transformed into a system of algebraic equations relating the eigenvalues of the iteration scheme to the Fourier wave number. The largest magnitude eigenvalue is known as the spectral radius of the system, which represents the asymptotic convergence rate of the iteration scheme.

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Previous work has applied Fourier analysis to deterministic methods, both with and without thermal-hydraulic feedback [5, 6]. However, stochastic methods have not been considered so thoroughly. In 2016, the convergence of Monte Carlo source iteration with acceleration was analysed [7]. However, it was assumed that infinite particles were used per neutron generation, therefore statistical errors were neglected. In 2024, Monte Carlo source iteration was analysed with the addition of thermal-hydraulic feedback [8]. While statistical errors were somewhat considered, the exact effects of statistical noise on the spectral radius were not studied.

In this work, Fourier analysis is applied to TRRM in order to predict how system parameters impact the convergence of the iteration scheme. The approach taken does not neglect the statistical errors that appear due to the stochastic nature of TRRM. The predictions are then compared to measured results obtained using the neutronics code SCONE [3, 9]. The subsequent sections are organised as follows: Section 2 presents the definitions of the problem to be analysed, Section 3 presents the Fourier analysis for this iteration scheme, Section 4 discusses the resulting predictions and presents comparisons with measured results, and Section 5 presents the conclusions and potential future work.

2. DEFINITION OF THE MODEL PROBLEM

The steady-state neutron transport equation can be written as:

$$\Omega \cdot \nabla \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega, E) + \Sigma_t \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega, E) = \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega, E' \rightarrow E) \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega', E') + \frac{\chi(\mathbf{r}, E)}{4\pi k_{\text{eff}}} \int_0^\infty dE' \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E') \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega', E'). \quad (1)$$

All variables have their usual meanings. A number of simplifying assumptions can be applied to Eq. (1) ahead of the Fourier analysis. We assume that the problem is 1D, mono-energetic, homogeneous, and has isotropic scattering and periodic boundary conditions, leading to:

$$\mu \frac{\partial \psi(x, \mu)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_t \psi(x, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\Sigma_s + \frac{\bar{\nu} \Sigma_f}{k_{\text{eff}}} \right) \phi(x), \quad (2)$$

where the scalar flux ϕ is given by:

$$\phi(x) = \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x, \mu) d\mu. \quad (3)$$

TRRM is a stochastic variation of the method of characteristics [10], where instead of using a fixed set of characteristic tracks and angular quadrature, a set of tracks is randomly sampled each iteration. Each power iteration, TRRM proceeds by solving the characteristic form of the transport equation across N rays, each of which has its starting position and direction sampled uniformly in space and angle. The initial angular flux of each ray is unknown, therefore some approximation must be made for the starting angular flux of each ray. The usual approach is to set the initial angular flux for each energy group equal to the local isotropic neutron source. This approximation introduces a bias, but this can be mitigated through the use of a “dead length”, where the ray is traced through the geometry for a user-specified distance without updating the scalar flux. Following the dead length, the ray traverses a user-defined “active length” where it does contribute to scalar flux estimates. Following this active length, the ray is terminated and the calculation proceeds either by sampling another ray or by completing the source iteration. Each ray has a uniform quadrature weight: in 3D this is $w = \frac{4\pi V}{ND_a}$ where V is the volume of the geometry and D_a is the active length of the ray. In 1D this reduces to $w = \frac{2L}{ND_a}$ where L is the problem length.

In TRRM, in the fine mesh limit, the scalar flux at point x , $\phi(x)$, is estimated by a Monte Carlo sum over the change in the angular fluxes of rays which are active when they strike that point, plus a source term:

$$\phi(x) = \frac{2L}{ND_a \Sigma_t} \sum_{n=1}^N \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(-\frac{d\psi_n}{ds} \right) \delta(x - x'_n - \mu_n s) + \frac{2q}{\Sigma_t} \quad (4)$$

Here, n denotes the index of a given ray, ψ_n is the angular flux of that ray, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, x'_n is the ray's starting position, s is the distance that the ray has traversed from that position, μ_n is the ray's direction cosine, $q(x)$ is the local isotropic source, $D = D_a + D_d$, and D_a and D_d are the active and dead lengths, respectively.

From the characteristic formulation of the transport equation, assuming constant cross sections, the angular flux along a given ray is:

$$\psi_n(x'_n, s, \mu_n) = \psi_0(x'_n, \mu_n) e^{-\Sigma_t s} + \int_0^s q(x'_n + s' \mu_n) e^{-\Sigma_t (s-s')} ds' \quad (5)$$

where ψ_0 is the angular flux at the beginning of the ray. As the starting angular flux of a ray is unknown, it is conventional to approximate it as $\psi_0(x'_n, \mu_n) = q(x'_n) / \Sigma_t$.

Eqs. (4) and (5) can be combined into a source iteration scheme as:

$$q^{(l)}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\Sigma_s + \frac{\nu \Sigma_f}{k_{\text{eff}}^{(l)}} \right) \phi^{(l)}(x) \quad (6a)$$

$$\psi_n^{(l+\frac{1}{2})}(x'_n, s, \mu_n) = \frac{q^{(l)}(x'_n)}{\Sigma_t} e^{-\Sigma_t s} + \int_0^s q^{(l)}(x'_n + s' \mu_n) e^{-\Sigma_t (s-s')} ds \quad (6b)$$

$$\phi^{(l+1)}(x) = \frac{2L}{ND_a \Sigma_t} \sum_{n=1}^N \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(-\frac{d\psi_n}{ds} \right)^{(l+\frac{1}{2})} \delta(x - x'_n - \mu_n s) + \frac{2q^{(l)}(x)}{\Sigma_t} \quad (6c)$$

Here l denotes the source iteration number. $k_{\text{eff}}^{(l)}$ is calculated each source iteration as the ratio of the total neutron production rate to total neutron absorption rate.

3. LINEARISATION AND FOURIER ANALYSIS

Having defined the iteration scheme, the Fourier analysis proceeds by linearising the scalar flux around the converged solution, Φ_0 , as:

$$\phi^{(l)}(x) = \Phi_0 + \phi_1^{(l)}(x) \quad (7)$$

where $\phi_1^{(l)}$ is the iterative error. The Fourier ansatz is given by

$$\phi_1^{(l)}(x) = \sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \omega_p^l \phi_p^0 e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t x} \quad (8a)$$

$$q^{(l)}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_t \phi^{(l)} \quad (8b)$$

where ω_p is the Fourier eigenvalue of the p -th mode, λ_p is the Fourier wave number, and ϕ_p^0 is the initial amplitude of a given flux error mode. For periodic geometry, $\lambda_p = \frac{2p\pi}{L\Sigma_t}$ for $p \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$. We note that ω_p^l is an abuse of notation: as ω_p is a random variable, this should be more formally written as $\prod_{l'=1}^l \omega_p^{(l')}$

where $\omega_p^{(l')}$ is the amplification factor evaluated on the l' -th iteration. Use of Eqs. (8) along with Eq. (6b) produces the ansatz for the angular flux:

$$\psi_1^{(l+\frac{1}{2})}(x'_n, s, \mu_n) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \omega_p^l \phi_p^0 e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t x'} \frac{e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu s} + i\lambda_p \mu e^{-\Sigma_t s}}{1 + i\lambda_p \mu}. \quad (9)$$

Substituting this into Eq. (6c), Fourier transforming to isolate a given mode m , evaluating the x integral, and cancelling terms gives:

$$\omega_m = 1 + \frac{1}{ND_a} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_m} \right)^l \frac{\phi_p^0}{\phi_m^0} e^{i(\lambda_p - \lambda_m) \Sigma_t x} \frac{i\lambda_p \mu_n}{1 + i\lambda_p \mu_n} \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu_n s} \right) e^{-i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu_n s}, \quad (10)$$

where we have consumed the Dirac delta by setting $x' = x - \mu s$. The largest absolute value of ω_m (with respect to m) is the spectral radius, ρ , of the iterative scheme. Since Eq. (10) contains a stochastic sum, the spectral radius is no longer a deterministic quantity, but a random variable. For TRRM (and Monte Carlo alike), the predicted spectral radius for a system will have a mean value, along with an associated variance that is dependent on the number of rays (particles) used in a given simulation.

The mean value of ω_m can be calculated by applying the expectation operator to Equation (10) and applying the Law of Large Numbers (LLN) to convert the Monte Carlo sum into its corresponding integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\omega_m] &= 1 + \frac{1}{2LD_a} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \int_0^L dx' \sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_m} \right)^l \frac{\phi_p^0}{\phi_m^0} e^{i(\lambda_p - \lambda_m) \Sigma_t x'} \frac{i\lambda_p \mu}{1 + i\lambda_p \mu} \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu s} \right) e^{-i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu s} \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2D_a} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \frac{i\lambda_m \mu}{1 + i\lambda_m \mu} \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t(1+i\lambda_m \mu)s} - 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{\arctan(\lambda_m)}{\lambda_m} + \frac{1}{2D_a} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \frac{i\lambda_m \mu}{1 + i\lambda_m \mu} \int_{D_d}^D ds e^{-\Sigma_t(1+i\lambda_m \mu)s}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where we have used the facts that $\mu \sim \text{Uniform}(-1, 1)$ and $x' \sim \text{Uniform}(0, L)$.

The variance of ω_m can be calculated as:

$$\sigma^2[\omega_m - 1] = \frac{1}{N} \left(\mathbb{E}[|\omega_m - 1|^2] - |\mathbb{E}[\omega_m - 1]|^2 \right), \quad (12)$$

where the second moment can be calculated similarly to the first moment as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[|\omega_m - 1|^2] &= \frac{1}{2LD_a^2} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \int_0^L dx' \\ &\quad \left[\sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_m} \right)^l \frac{\phi_p^0}{\phi_m^0} e^{i(\lambda_p - \lambda_m) \Sigma_t x'} \frac{\lambda_p \mu}{1 + i\lambda_p \mu} \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu s} \right) e^{-i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu s} \right] \\ &\quad \times \left[\sum_{\substack{q=-\infty \\ q \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_q}{\omega_m} \right)^l \frac{\phi_q^{0,+}}{\phi_m^{0,+}} e^{-i(\lambda_q - \lambda_m) \Sigma_t x'} \frac{\lambda_q \mu}{1 - i\lambda_q \mu} \int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{-i\lambda_q \Sigma_t \mu s} \right) e^{i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu s} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Here the † superscript denotes complex conjugation. The x' integral enforces that $p = q$, reducing the double sum to a single sum:

$$\mathbb{E}[|\omega_m - 1|^2] = \frac{1}{2D_a^2} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \sum_{\substack{p=-\infty \\ p \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left| \frac{\omega_p}{\omega_m} \right|^{2l} \left| \frac{\phi_p^0}{\phi_m^0} \right|^2 \frac{\lambda_p^2 \mu^2}{1 + \lambda_p^2 \mu^2} \left[\int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu s} \right) e^{-i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu s} \right] \times \left[\int_{D_d}^D ds \left(e^{-\Sigma_t s} - e^{-i\lambda_p \Sigma_t \mu s} \right) e^{i\lambda_m \Sigma_t \mu s} \right]. \quad (14)$$

The expression for the variance is challenging to evaluate without employing approximations. This is because ω_m is implicit in its own variance. The variance also contains an infinite sum of other randomly varying amplification factors, ω_p . Finally, and unusually for Fourier analysis, there is an explicit dependence on the initial condition; this reflects correlation between iterations. For the dominant mode, the only necessary approximation is that a large number of iterations have passed: this allows the elimination of all higher modes from the summation. The mode $m' = -m$ must be preserved because $|\omega_m| = |\omega_{-m}|$. All presented evaluations of the variance assume this is the case and also take $|\phi_m^0| = |\phi_{-m}^0|$. The accurate evaluation of the variance for higher modes will be the subject of future work.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Predictions

From Eqs. (11) and (12), it is possible to predict the dependence of the spectral radius and its variance on system parameters, such as the active length and dead length of the rays.

Fig. 1 shows how the ray active length affects the mean of ω_m and the standard deviation of ρ for an example problem. For the same problem, Fig. 2 shows how the dead length affects the same quantities. Here “Source iteration” is the standard source iteration result of $\omega_m = \arctan(\lambda_m) / \lambda_m$, and is included for comparison.

Figure 1. Predicted mean of ω_m and standard deviation of ρ when varying the ray active length D_a . $L = 10$ cm, $D_d = 1$ cm, $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm⁻¹, $N = 1000$, $l = 20$

From these figures, a number of observations can be made:

- The mean convergence rate of random ray is a small correction to that of source iteration, with the correction tending to zero as both D_a and D_d increase.

Figure 2. Predicted mean of ω_m and standard deviation of ρ when varying the ray dead length D_d . $L = 10$ cm, $D_a = 1$ cm, $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$, $N = 1000$, $l = 20$

- The variance also depends on the ray length, and tend to constants as both D_a and D_d increase.
- The mean value of ω_m is predicted to always be less than 1, suggesting unconditional stability. This is not strictly the case, however, as it is possible that if the mean and variance are sufficiently high, “iterative transients” may emerge where error modes grow. In extreme cases, this could lead to negative fluxes and therefore instability. As a result, in order to ensure stability, both the mean spectral radius and its variance should be minimised.

4.2. Verification

In order to verify the predicted results, a simple 1D slab geometry was created in the neutronics code SCONE [3, 9]. As our analysis has not yet accounted for discretisation or the stochastic estimation of volumes in TRRM [11], our numerical comparisons used a fine mesh and exact volume estimates to mitigate this inconsistency.

The Fourier mode eigenvalues are measured by taking the Fourier transform of the iterative error ($\phi^{(l)} - \Phi_0$), and computing the ratio of these errors on subsequent iterations. This is done for multiple independent runs from which averages and variances may be computed. For all problems considered here, the spectral radius corresponds to the Fourier eigenvalue for $m = 1$.

Fig. 3 shows a comparison between predicted and measured results when varying D_a , with the standard source iteration result shown for comparison. This problem has $L = 20$ cm, 500 mesh cells, $N = 5000$, $D_d = 2$ cm and $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$. The results were averaged over 50 independent runs. Both the measured mean and standard deviation results show good agreement with predictions, and confirm a noticeable deviation from the standard source iteration result for small D_a .

Similarly, Fig. 4 shows a comparison between predicted and measured results when varying D_d , for a problem with $L = 20$ cm, 500 mesh cells, $N = 5000$, $D_a = 1$ cm and $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$. Very good agreement is also observed here.

The predictions for higher order modes were also compared to measurements. The problem analysed has $L = 200$ cm, 1000 mesh cells, $N = 10000$, $D_d = 2$ cm, $D_a = 2$ cm, and $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$. The results were averaged over 100 independent runs and the results for the first seven error modes are shown in in Figure 5. The mean results show very good agreement with the predicted values, and also confirm the expected deviation from the standard source iteration result. As mentioned in Section 3, evaluating the predictions of the variances of higher order modes will be the subject of future work, therefore they

Figure 3. Comparison of predicted and measured ρ while varying D_a . $L = 20$ cm, $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$, 500 mesh cells, $N = 5000$, $D_d = 2$ cm, $l = 20$. Average of 50 runs.

Figure 4. Comparison of predicted and measured ρ while varying D_a . $L = 20$ cm, $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$, 500 mesh cells, $N = 5000$, $D_d = 1$ cm, $l = 20$. Average of 50 runs.

are not included here.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the convergence properties of TRRM were analysed through Fourier analysis. Predictions of the mean and variance of the spectral radius were derived, including the dependence on parameters such as the active and dead lengths of the rays. Predictions suggest, as perhaps expected, that the spectral radius of TRRM is a small additive factor upon the standard source iteration result, with the additive term tending to zero for large ray lengths. Predictions were compared to results measured using the neutronics code SCONE, and the results for the mean amplification factors all show very good agreement with theory. The standard deviation of the spectral radius was also found to closely match predictions; this is the first time, to our knowledge, that a Fourier analysis has explicitly accounted for stochastic effects.

Future work will explore the variance of higher order error modes, account for geometry discretisation, and expand this methodology to include multiphysics and convergence acceleration.

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Figure 5. Comparison of measured and predicted ω_m . $L = 200$ cm, $\Sigma_t = 1$ cm $^{-1}$, 1000 mesh cells, 10000 rays, $D_d = 2$ cm, $D_a = 2$ cm, $l = 20$, average of 100 runs.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. R. Tramm, K. S. Smith, B. Forget, and A. R. Siegel. "The Random Ray Method for neutral particle transport." *Journal of Computational Physics*, **volume 342**, pp. 229–252 (2017).
- [2] J. R. Tramm. *Development of The Random Ray Method of Neutral Particle Transport for High-Fidelity Nuclear Reactor Simulation*. Ph.D. thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (2018).
- [3] P. Cosgrove and J. R. Tramm. "The Random Ray Method Versus Multigroup Monte Carlo: The Method of Characteristics in OpenMC and SCONE." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 198**, pp. 1739–1758 (2024).
- [4] S. Choi and B. Kochunas. "Coarse mesh finite difference acceleration of the random ray method." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 210**, p. 110848 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454924005115>.
- [5] M. L. Adams and E. W. Larsen. "Fast iterative methods for discrete-ordinates particle transport calculations." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 40**, pp. 3–159 (2002).
- [6] B. Kochunas, A. Fitzgerald, and E. Larsen. "Fourier analysis of iteration schemes for k-eigenvalue transport problems with flux-dependent cross sections." *Journal of Computational Physics*, **volume 345**, pp. 294–307 (2017).
- [7] K. P. Keady. *Acceleration and Stabilization Methods for Monte Carlo Reactor Core k-Eigenvalue Problems*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Michigan (2016).
- [8] K. Li, N. An, H. Luo, J. Liang, D. She, Z. Liu, and K. Wang. "Stability Analyses of the Monte Carlo Neutron Transport with Thermal-Hydraulics Feedback." In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR-2024*. American Nuclear Society, San Francisco, California, United States (2024).
- [9] V. Raffuzzi, P. Cosgrove, and M. A. Kowalski. "Status of the SCONE Monte Carlo neutron transport code." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 227**, p. 112015 (2026).
- [10] J. Askew. "A characteristics formulation of the neutron transport equation in complicated geometries." Technical report, No. AEEW-M-1108, UK Atomic Energy Establishment (1972).
- [11] J. R. Tramm, A. R. Siegel, A. L. Lund, and P. K. Romano. "A comparison of stochastic mesh cell volume computation strategies for the random ray method of neutral particle transport." In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR-2020*. American Nuclear Society, Cambridge, United Kingdom (2020).